

Trivalent Metal Fluoberyllates and Alums : Ferric Fluoberyllate and Alums

A. K. Baral, H. K. Saha and N. Ray

H. C. Kawecki¹ showed that the reaction,

$3\text{BeO} + 2\text{Na}_2\text{FeF}_6 = 3\text{Na}_2\text{BeF}_4 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ is feasible in the solid state. F. Feigl and A. Schaeffer² observed that FeF_6^{3-} ion responds to the test of Fe^{3+} ion in presence of beryllium ion. It has been investigated by the present authors that FeF_6^{3-} ion in presence of Be^{2+} ion forms BeF_4^{2-} ion in solution which can be precipitated as BaBeF_4 in between pH 2 to 3. Beryllium ions have a great tendency to form stable complex BeF_4^{2-} ions, and even beryllium fluoride also exists in aqueous solution as beryllium fluoberyllate³.

Thus, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3$ may be formed in preference to the formation of FeF_6^{3-} ion in a solution containing Be^{2+} , F^- and Fe^{3+} ions. The preparation and properties of free chromic and Aluminium fluoberyllates⁴, have already been reported. In this communication, preparation and properties of ferric fluoberyllate and the corresponding ferric alums have been investigated. We used fluoberyllic acid and the corresponding metal hydroxide as the starting material which gave satisfactory results. The composition has mainly been established by analytical methods.

All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Methods of Analysis— BeF_4^{2-} was determined as BaBeF_4 by precipitating with 5% barium chloride solution at pH 4 and then heating to constant weight at 115°-120°.

In the filtrate iron was determined directly after reduction to ferrous state followed by titration with standard potassium dichromate using barium diphenylamine sulfonate as indicator.

Alkali metals were determined as their sulfates after evaporating off fluorine with conc. H_2SO_4 and precipitating beryllium and iron with ammonia.

Fluoberyllic acid—Fluoberyllic acid was prepared according to the method of Ray et al⁵.

1. H. C. Kawecki, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1946, 89, 133.
2. F. Feigl and A. Schaeffer, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 351.
3. Fluocomplexes of Beryllium—A. K. Baral, H. Saha, N. Ray, *Journ. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2490.
4. Trivalent metal fluoberyllates—Aluminium and Chromic fluoberyllates and alums, A. K. Baral, H. Saha, N. Ray, Communicated to this Journal.
5. Fluoberyllic acid—T. K. Ghosh, T. N. Chakravarty and N. Ray, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 12.

Density—Densities were determined by floatation of alum crystals using suitable mixtures of liquids, like methylene iodide and benzene. The results are given in gms/ml.

Ferric Fluoberyllate, $Fe_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ —Ferric hydroxide was precipitated with dilute ammonia solution, from an aqueous solution of ferric nitrate and washed repeatedly with large volumes of water by decantation, till almost free from nitrate and finally filtered and dried.

A sample of about 8 gms. of moist Ferric hydroxide was dissolved in concentrated fluoberyllic acid. The clear solution had a pH of about 2-2.5. This solution on concentration in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid a gummy mass was obtained. The gummy mass was found to be soluble in water and the solution responded to the test of Fe^{3+} ion and BeF_4^{2-} ion. The solution was again evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid, the concentrated solution was treated with anhydrous alcohol. A pale yellow gelatinous mass was precipitated, which was filtered and dried.

0.1718 gm. of the substance on analysis gave 0.2294 gm. of $BaBeF_4$, and required 20.55 ml. of 6863N/20 potassium dichromate solution.

Found, Fe=22.94%, BeF_4^{2-} =51.01%. Calculated for, $Fe_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot 7H_2O$: Fe=22.71%, BeF_4^{2-} =51.85%.

The substance was found to be highly hygroscopic and easily soluble in water. On keeping, the solution assumes a brown colour, but becomes paler on addition of fluoberyllic acid. On heating the crystals, acid fumes were found to evolve which was hydrogen fluoride vapour (tested with zirconium alizarin-s paper).

Fluoberyllate ferric-ammonium alum : $Fe_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot (NH_4)_2BeF_4 \cdot 24H_2O$ —An aqueous solution of 0.25 gm. of ammonium fluoberyllate was mixed with 1.1 gm. of ferric fluoberyllate. The solution was kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated H_2SO_4 . A brown yellow syrupy solution was obtained which produced overgrowth on a small octahedral crystal of $Fe_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot (NH_4)SO_4 \cdot 24H_2O$. But the syrupy solution itself did not crystallise on further evaporation in vacuo and set to a brown-yellow glassy mass. All attempts to crystallise the fluoberyllate ferric-ammonium alum resulted in a failure.

Fluoberyllate Ferric-Rubidium alum : $Fe_2(BeF_4)_3 \cdot Rb_2BeF_4 \cdot 24H_2O$ —A sample of 0.35 gm. of Rubidium fluoberyllate in aqueous solution was mixed with 1 gm. of ferric fluoberyllate in solution. The solution was acidified with fluoberyllic acid. The pH of the solution was 2.5-3. The solution was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The crystals obtained were examined under microscope and found to be octahedral in shape.

0.0345 gm. of the substance required 2.05 ml. of $0.6863\left(\frac{N}{20}\right)K_2Cr_2O_7$.

0.1064 gm. of the substance gave 0.0830 gm. of BaBeF_4 , and

0.1310 gm. of material gave 0.0345 gm. of Rubidium sulfate.

Found, Fe=11.28%, BeF_4^{2-} =29.82%, Rb=16.86%. Calculated for, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Rb}_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Fe=10.91%, BeF_4^{2-} =30.26%, Rb=16.68%.

Density at $30^\circ = 2.02$.

The crystals are very pale yellow in colour. On exposure to air they acquire a bluish green tinge and are easily soluble in water. In the powdered form the crystals rapidly effluoresce. The loss in weight corresponds to the loss of thirteen molecules of water on keeping in a desiccator over silica gel. The crystal shape is lost with the loss of water molecules. On heating the crystals HF vapour was found to evolve.

Fluoberyllate Ferric-Caesium Alum : $\text{Fe}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Cs}_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ —An aqueous solution of 0.63 gm of Cs_2BeF_4 was mixed with 1 gm. of Ferric fluoberyllate. The solution was acidified with fluoberyllic acid. The pH of the solution was 2.5-3. The solution was then evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The first crop of crystals were found to be caesium fluoberyllate which were filtered off. The filtrate when crystallised in vacuo over conc. H_2SO_4 gave a second crop of crystals which on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape.

0.0244 gm. of the material required 1.15 ml. of $0.6863\left(\frac{\text{N}}{20}\right)\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.

0.0528 gm. of the substance gave 0.0374 gm. of BaBeF_4 , and

0.0938 gm. gave 0.0308 gm. of caesium sulfate.

Found, Fe=9.902%, BeF_4^{2-} =27.08%, Cs=24.12%. Calculated for, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Cs}_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Fe=9.87%, BeF_4^{2-} =27.46%, Cs=23.75%.

Density at $30^\circ = 2.31$.

The crystals are very pale yellow and sparingly soluble in water. On exposure to air these acquire a greenish tinge. In the powdered form the crystals slowly effluoresce and the crystal shape is lost with the loss of water molecules. On heating the crystals HF vapour was found to evolve.